

Co-design with operators – developing meaningful XR and digital interface solutions

Challenges and solutions:

Our contribution within THEIA-XR focuses on developing a transdisciplinary co-design approach for XR applications in professional, safety-critical environments. Together with snow groomer, excavator and reach stacker operators, we explored how technology could support not only efficiency and safety, but also a positive user experience.

Through contextual interviews and iterative workshops, we gained a deep understanding of the realities of daily work. Together with the operators, we developed new concepts, including ambient light bars around the windscreen to visualize nearby objects, laser-based projections of excavation boundaries and power lines, and additional functions for the in-cabin tablet.

Our process was guided by scenario-based design. Starting from a scenario that described the operators' initial working situation, we gradually extended it with new ideas. Finally, these ideas were visualised as early prototypes for XR functions and tablet interfaces.

Impact:

The transdisciplinary co-design approach was applied for the first time in this particular field. It led to the creation of innovative and meaningful concepts. Feedback from operators confirmed that these new ideas could make their work easier and safer. Moving forward, these concepts could be further refined and implemented in collaboration with operators and technical experts. We strongly encourage the continued use of co-design methods in shaping the future of XR applications.

Figure 1: XR and digital interface function concepts for excavators and snow groomers. Visualization in cooperation with TUD and Creanex.

KEY BENEFITS

Insights for future transdisciplinary co-design in industrial environments

Realistic scenarios and concepts co-created with operators

XR and digital interface concepts enhancing safety, clarity and user confidence

